

Considering impact strategies in historical and musicological research projects

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Introduction: What is impact? What is it not?

The notion of impact refers to the deep consequences of academic research on the general public, outside the scientific community. Impact can be cultural, economic, environmental, social, health-related, legal, or even technological. In the United Kingdom, it represents a key issue for university funding, meticulously documented for submission to the *Research Excellence Framework*¹ and demanding long-term strategic planning. For example, in the context of the University of York impact case study « St Stephen’s Chapel and the House of Commons: changing historical practice, enhancing understanding, and influencing restoration in the Palace of Westminster² », the stated objectives go far beyond the scope of scientific publications in favour of a triple ambition: « changing historical practice, enhancing understanding, and influencing restoration » in partnership with the UK Parliament.³

In Europe, this concept is still more ambiguous and often mistakenly equated with scientific valorization related to publishing results. The current document, written following two days of conferences jointly organized by Le Studium Loire Valley - Institute for Advanced Studies and the RicercarLab - Centre d’Études Supérieures de la Renaissance⁴, under the direction of John Cooper and Philippe Vendrix, aims to clarify the notion of impact within the scope of history, musicology, and interactions between the two disciplines. It draws on the experiences of colleagues from France, Belgium, the UK and USA to consider how to integrate impact effectively and authentically into research project proposals, while taking into account the prerogatives of the European Union with initiatives such as New European Bauhaus (NEB)⁵, emphasizing sustainability in the context of environmental impact in the EU.

It is integral to our thought process to highlight the importance that the subjects themselves hold when thinking about impact. For instance, discovering a forgotten Pharaoh's tomb might hold broad appeal and constitute a worldwide event, while discovering a brand new Gesualdo madrigal might not even get you a few pages in a slightly popular music review. Similarly, the choice of focus — whether grand and well-known locations like the Palace of Westminster, or more modest ones like Châteaudun — deeply affects the accessibility and the possibility for audiences to identify with the scientific subject. A well-known « national treasure » might generate widespread public interest, but at the same time present significant logistical challenges; smaller and less prominent sites, by contrast, often allow for easier and closer collaboration with local communities.

While it is important to bear these considerations in mind, they should not overshadow the need to take impact into account in all stages of scientific projects, from initial planning to research, analysis and outputs. Impact can take place during the funded phase of a project, but frequently

¹ For more information, see « [How Research England supports research excellence](#) ».

² John Cooper, Rosemary Hill, Catriona Cooper, Miles Taylor, Tim Ayers, « St Stephen’s Chapel and the House of Commons: changing historical practice, enhancing understanding, and influencing restoration in the Palace of Westminster », [Research excellence framework 2021](#).

³ Impact case study: St Stephen’s Chapel and the House of Commons: changing historical practice, enhancing understanding, and influencing restoration in the Palace of Westminster.

⁴ Talks held this day include contributions from John Cooper (University of York UK), David Fiala (CESR-RicercarLab), Richard Freedman (Haverford College USA), Kerry McCarthy (independent scholar), Anthony Musson (Historic Royal Palaces UK), Philippe Vendrix (CESR-RicercarLab), Pascal Brioiist (CESR) and Magnus Williamson (Newcastle University UK).

⁵ For more information, see “New European Bauhaus” https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

develops after the research team has dispersed: this creates a positive legacy, but also poses challenges for the management and measuring of impact. In the UK, the underpinning research of the project also has to be published before impact can be said to derive from it: another challenge to be met. The experience of recent collaborative research including the AHRC-funded projects « St Stephen's Chapel Westminster » and « Listening to the Commons: The Sounds of Debate and the Experience of Women in Parliament c. 1800 » (the second of these a follow-on project specifically targeting impact) additionally demonstrates that devising and delivering impact can encourage unexpected research paths: the impact deriving from one pathway, but also stimulating subsequent and unanticipated strands of research. Consequently impact can allow us to imagine new ways of approaching the discipline, as well as sharing results with a wider audience with long-term influence on the perception of music history.

1. Impact-related issues

a. Why is it necessary to generate impact?

Over and above the academic evaluations that are necessary to obtain the funding inherent to the continuation of research, taking impact into account is invaluable for its long-term dissemination. It allows us to think about how we can share the results of our research and rethink our publishing practices beyond our usual ecosystem. How do we visualise and communicate rich data, or link musical data and history? What are our practices in investigating the specificities of a musical period? Finally, how can we actively engage the audience in crafting the research beyond standard period dissemination?

As a starting point, it is fundamental to consider the FAIR and OpenAccess policies ; while still undoubtedly tied to the research world, they constitute a solid basis for a free and interoperable access to data. In this regard, the *Gesualdo online* edition published by the RicercarLab aims to be an interoperable digital library that weaves links between sources, data on works and on individuals associated with Gesualdo:

While being a resource for researchers and performers, professionals and amateurs, but also a contribution to musicology as a science of data (like other disciplines such as archaeology, linguistics, etc.). Without this data science perspective, musicology risks not having a constructive (and strong) dialogue with the world of cultural and creative industries. This would be a missed opportunity, as the current cultural landscape is being visibly reconfigured⁶.

This project exemplifies the need to rethink scientific tools in terms of impact, in order to be able to engage in dialogue with extra-scientific communities. The case of *Gesualdo online* also shows us, however, that it can be difficult to foresee all the aspects of such a project, such as setting up a network to ensure satisfactory dissemination of tools and results. Thinking about impact from the inception of a project allows us to consider the global scope of scientific spin-offs, integrating their sharing into the very heart of the scientific proposal. Taking this a step further, it is thus possible to use societal observations linked to the state-of-the-art of a discipline as a starting point for questioning it, in a sort of reverse engineering process made possible by conscientizing the importance of impact.

⁶ Philippe Vendrix, « [Gesualdo online ; the economic model of a digital music edition](#) », p. 16

b. Impact as a vector of identity: how to address communities?

Implementing impact strategies must aspire to unite communities around perennial scientific themes; it is therefore important that events organized as part of a project gather a wide audience in contrast to a *niche* of researchers. In fact, we should specifically commit to targeting audiences peripheral to the world of research in order to demonstrate inclusivity in changing the understanding of historical and/or musical facts in a thorough way.

Among numerous impact cases studies, the notion of identity is regularly mentioned. It is a focal point around which we can build projects, both from the point of view of impact and of the research itself. We can thus question the nature of identity in the context of the study of early music, where the coalescence of many parameters shapes the political and historiographical role of a work, as well the identity — both as essence as performability —, of its performers, composer and the people to whom it is tied. By attempting to recreate the performative contexts in an immersive way, it seems possible more thoroughly to connect the identities being studied with the identities of the audience.

Even more accessible to a range of communities (for instance, people's homes) than live performance is the video medium, whether through films or documentaries. However, working on this kind of media comes with challenges such as very high production costs and difficulties in translation (as discussed below). We can nevertheless call on the experience of John Cooper, drawing on his work as a historical consultant for film and television and its impact potential. For instance *The Spanish Princess* (for Starz television), an historical fiction targeted at a broad audience, was also the first drama of its kind to bring Black Tudors to the screen — an authentic story, connecting to questions of identity in the modern day. Meanwhile the BBC series *Gunpowder* made use of St Stephen's Chapel project expertise and 3D digital models to influence production choices, as documented in the impact case study which resulted. A follow-up interview with John Cooper also appeared in *The Times* newspaper, defending the historical authenticity of depictions of sectarian violence in the series.

These projects demonstrate how the showcase of *real* history can help engage unexpected audiences. Depending on the context, historical consultancy might be an easier pathway to impact than the production of historical documentaries. Being able to imagine further connections with the Creative and Cultural Industries⁷ is also an important topic to discuss.

c. Issues with translating scientific expertise to impact

In order to give an account of the scientific work carried out as part of a research project, a process of translation needs to be considered to demonstrate the depth of the issues studied. This rendering process does not only target the purpose of the project in terms of impact, — the communities identified during the prospects, that will be met during later events —, but also the various agents involved in the logistical organisation of events, external partners such as musicians and singers, sound technicians, *etc.*, in short, all those who make the impact possible by internally shaping it. Mutual understanding is thus a key resource for healthy exchanges and helps to give a new impulse to the discipline, from the inside. One should also be wary not to confuse this work with cultural mediation, which dwells in explaining artistic practices through example and talks.

Despite the efforts made, the vast majority of researchers report that there is still a palpable resistance from the public to musical heritage, whereas patrimonial and historiographical

⁷ A worthy partner can be found in the PEPR ICCARE, of which one of the main investigators is Solveig Serre, senior researcher at CESR.

elements seem to be more easily perceived and integrated into existing knowledge. Although this can be explained by a tendency to feel more at ease with historical figures and their *identities* than with musicians, even less than with works and their contexts, this still shows the reach of the work needed to make a profound and authentic impact on diverse communities throughout the presentation of musical works.

Moreover, unlike its historical counterpart, musicology often tends to be viewed negatively by the scientific community, particularly in terms of its ability to legitimize an impact on the public. For example, rejections of scientific projects have sometimes been justified in reports by a simple lack of interest of the reviewers in 16th century music, without any other explanation; this can be a major problem with funders with multi-disciplinary peer reviewers. In a context where funding is becoming increasingly competitive, these situations lead us to consider multidisciplinary projects in order to integrate the musical experience into social, political and historiographical frameworks.

In this respect, the example of the « Henry VIII on Tour: Landscapes. Communities and Performance » project⁸ led by Anthony Musson with John Cooper, Magnus Williamson and Kate Giles, is worth considering. Their impact strategy is structured around four main areas unified by the reconstruction of Henry VIII's geographical journeys:

- Raising awareness for local communities of the existence of places crossed by Henry VIII through site visits.
- Archaeology of pre-identified sites: discovery of the past combined with community sharing open to all ages, enhanced by digital visualisations of the site.
- Reconstruction of ceremonies of progress including actors and reproducing banquets: inclusion of communities in the stories of Henry VIII's hosting through convivial and festive moments.
- Musical performances of newly edited music, in accordance with the corresponding liturgy, given in pre-identified places of progress: participants and communities experience service enactments.

While some of these suggestions may seem very far away from the European researchers' daily practice, they constitute a key standard for the UK practice of impact and show us that interdisciplinarity and collaboration between researchers and a wide range of seasoned professionals are absolutely fundamental to interfacing with communities. It is thus necessary to plan for these tasks as soon as the project proposal is submitted, since they require a high level of financial and inter-personal investment, as well as carrying out preparatory surveys prior to submitting funding applications. Those will enable us to identify the key operators with whom to collaborate : associations, theatre companies, archaeological centres, but even ecclesiastical communities or caterers, as seen in *Henry VIII on Tour's* banquets ! Having already strong links tied with the communities, they have much to offer to us in terms of better understanding of impact.

2. How can we further generate impact ?

a. A virtuous relationship to the environment

Considering the audience is one thing, but it is also important to think about how research projects fit into the communities' environments. Drawing on historiographical data is a first step

⁸ For more informations, see "Henry on tour; the progresses of Henry VIII": <https://henryontour.uk/>

towards rediscovering heritage sites, as those places can hold significant meaning for individuals, highlighting the connection between the appreciation of places and mental health. In this regard, music seems to be a perfect candidate for crafting the sonic ecology of a place through imaginative use of sound and space through a real musicological expertise. A project like « Listening to the Commons » is testimony to how impact can stimulate new research ideas rather than dictating the research, and allows the building of further links between the research fellows, unexplored places and new communities :

- A project team combining historical, acoustic, and digital humanities expertise succeeded in showing that, thanks to a ventilator driven through the old House of Commons ceiling, women (formally excluded from political life) could access debates in the Commons with in some cases a better listening experience than the male MPs down below. The study covers the period from 1820 to 1834, taking the overall chronology of the project to six centuries. Twenty-five tickets were available in the spaces accessed through the ventilation ducts, and it was possible to buy drinks, making it a social space. Two sketches of the space by women survive.
- In 2018, the *Voice & Vote* exhibition in Westminster Hall (107,000 visitors) recreated a replica of the ventilator, simulating how women may have experienced the sound of the House of Commons. The exhibition was curated by senior parliamentary staff, but dialogue with the research project enabled them to upscale the visitor experience with ‘authentic’ sound : one example of the dynamic relationship between host institutions and research-derived impact. A historic debate on the slave trade was also staged within the Commons chamber, drawing on project expertise and calling on Members of Parliament and parliamentary staff as ‘actors’. Two concerts of the sacred music of Nicholas Ludford were also performed, drawing on the Parliamentary choir and the choir of Gonville and Caius College Cambridge, in spaces associated with St Stephen’s Chapel : putting music probably composed for pre-Reformation St Stephen’s back into its original space. Events were filmed, and also audio-recorded for use in future acoustic modelling. These events wove a strong connection with two communities: visitors to the Palace of Westminster, and the politicians and staff who work there. Feedback forms showed that the exhibition played a role in profoundly changing attitudes, as well as inspiring new stories and ideas.

While being highly successful manifestations in terms of impact, it must be stressed that the human and logistical cost of these events is colossal. Many events require legal authorization or the build-up of trust over many months, not to mention the staff mobilized as research support. It would therefore seem that the quality of impact obeys a circular logic that offers the best-endowed establishments the opportunity to organise more efficient impact strategies.

b. Drawing on our teaching experience

We also need to underline that an important problem lies in the disconnect between impact and the education of students at university. While the students display a real interest in the curriculum, it is difficult to reach them within the framework of research projects. Impact on the students whom we teach is not judged to be ‘impact’ according to the UK assessment criteria, even though this area could represent a real intersection between education and research. The irony is that the collaboration of students in various impact-related activities is a highly valuable asset, since they are often willing to volunteer, are more inclined to share their experiences with the public than senior researchers, and are able to reach out to their own networks in disseminating the research.

Impact can, however, take place in schools. One strand of the « Henry VIII on Tour » project has been dedicated to the formation of teachers and other work in schools: through the Historical Association Teacher Fellowship programme, and teaching lessons at a two-day project team residency at a school located in a former Tudor royal palace. The University of York research project and impact case study « *England's Immigrants, 1330-1550: Enhancing the Teaching of Migration through History Resources for Schools and Teachers* » went even further in sharing educational resources. Indeed, the research team was able to edit a resource that then allowed them to rewrite school level curriculum in an authentic way.⁹

c. Link with the creative cultural industries

Although music researchers are amplifying their efforts with endeavours to promote the results of scientific research to the public, they still inherently face resistance from funding institutions. When applications are submitted, it is not uncommon to come across remarks such as « *what's the point of having musical performance ?* »... It is therefore up to the researcher to rethink the term in order to give it an interdisciplinary value — by referencing the performance of « experimental archaeology », for example. In an era where sharing music has been completely rethought through the internet and streaming in particular, it seems more necessary than ever not to miss the step to connect to the cultural industries, so as not to become even more isolated than we already are.

Collaborating with *art-de-vivre* industry¹⁰ as well as fashion may seem far removed from our concerns; these collaborations do, however, make sense in the context of refined reconstructions of musical performances, bringing together newly rediscovered or edited music to all sorts of communities and identities interested in clothes. Although this might be truer in the UK, where history courses offer a very visual approach to the Renaissance, we still have many lanes to explore in order to offer immersive experiences that can raise the awareness of diverse communities.

Similarly, the world of sport can be influenced by research results. For example, Pascal Briost (CESR) can testify to a consultancy role in a Hollywood movie, in which recent studies on fencing had a profound influence on transforming perceptions and representation of the discipline. These early collaborations led to his expertise being sought in identifying suitable filming locations.

Another massive point of vigilance in the context of musicology lies in considering the violence of Artificial Intelligence in music production today. Where certain tools now allow music creation *ex nihilo*, aggregators such as Spotify distribute this music in favour of authentic creations so that around 40% of the music in playlists today is now AI. Given this situation, it seems to us that building impact should be focused on bringing the human experience back to the public while retaining awareness of the tools offered by AI. It is therefore difficult to imagine sharing the fruits of musicological research to the public without going through the performance of new editions or even recently discovered works, as well giving them a digital open access and incorporating neural network training in some of our processes, for example. In this regard, researchers have yet to imagine new immersive devices or trans-disciplinary valorisation apparatus without falling

⁹ For more informations, see “England’s Immigrants 1330 – 1550 ; Resident Aliens in the Late Middle Ages”: <https://www.englishimmigrants.com/>

¹⁰ A good example of this collaboration can be found in the project *Henry VIII on tour*, where banquets were recreated: <https://www.hrp.org.uk/hampton-court-palace/whats-on/henry-viiiis-kitchens/#gs.k8jaec>

in the *soundscape*s trap ; it indeed seems that those might not be a sufficient focal point for impact because of their very abstract nature.

Concluding thoughts

Through these various examples, we have been able to see that impact is a major factor for tomorrow's research in three main prospects. The first, which is inevitable, is its necessity through the funding applications' evaluation processes. The second is its virtuous nature, which encourages us to get closer to communities from which we have sometimes distanced ourselves too much, in order to understand their identities and integrate them into research from a heuristic point of view, realizing the structural richness of these interactions, pushing us to rethink our discipline. The final area is the development of state-of-the-art tools in collaboration with the cultural and creative industries. Although complex — as everything remains to be built — this last task is, beyond its impact, the key to ultimately fruitful relations between researchers and communities.